

PMODWRC CERTAINTY

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for radiative transfer calculations at the PMODWRC is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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Grant

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Researchers

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Organizations

Physikalisch-Meteorologische Observatorium Davos/World
Radiation Center

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [PMODWRC CERTAINTY](#)

Description:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [ec_____::EC|European Commission|EC](#)

Grants: [101137680](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Radiative transfer simulations

Radiative transfer calculations to estimate aerosol and clouds radiative effect using real datasets from past campaigns and Earth Care and also simulated scenes.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The calculations will be performed during the project as part of WP1 and WP2

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Spectral short wave and long wave irradiances at bottom of the atmosphere (BOA) and top of the atmosphere (TOA), and radiometric quantities profiles.

1.1.5 What is its format?

ascii

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and derive aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The following radiative transfer programs will be utilized (full or partly) to perform the needed calculations:

1) The libRadtran model, publicly available under GNU licence in:
<https://www.libradtran.org/doku.php>

2) The MCstar (Monte Carlo solver for 3D radiative transfer simulations),
available at: <http://157.82.240.167/~clastr/>,

3) MYSTIC/libradtran 3D simulations in collaboration with the developers (LMU)
and upon request from the developers

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers

Project partners, research community

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Simulations output will be provided through Zenodo linked to DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Metadata will be provided through Zenodo

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The NOA's metadata can be found in OPENAIRE (<https://explore.openaire.eu>) and EOSC-portal ([EOSC-portal.eu](https://eosc-portal.eu))

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Metadata can be harvested for data sharing through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo automatically register a DOI for a record once it is published

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Radiative transfer calculations for aerosol and clouds radiative effect

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is 2 years from the moment of publication of the dataset.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

We will compare the simulated data with available measurements.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

10000

Swiss Franc

- Storage
- Re-use

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

Data will be provided through Zenodo

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Stelios Kazadzis (orcid:0000-0003-1031-0216)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository in Zenodo. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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